

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B293
Date: 12 June 2007
Take Off 09:41:05
Landing: 13:34:45
Flight Time 3h 53m 40s

Campaign: GERBIL – instrument test flight

Operating Area: South Coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Joanne Green	Directflight
4	CCM2 / Core Chem. / CDP	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
7	Mission Scientist 2	Ben Johnson	Met Office
8	Mission Scientist training 1	John Marsham	Leeds University
9	Mission Scientist training 2	Christian Grams	Leeds University
10	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
11	DEIMOS 1	Dave Pollard	Met Office
12	DEIMOS 2	Rob King	Met Office
14	Neph / PSAP / SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
15	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
16	Core Chem training	Stuart Heath	FAAM
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B293 Track 12-JUN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B293

Date: 12 Jun 07

Project: GERBIL (instrument test flight)

Location: South Coast / Thames Estuary

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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092352		INU	0.37 kft	125	to navigate
094105		T/O	0.36 kft	212	Cranfield
094125		psap	0.75 kft	217	pump off
094155		twc	1.1 kft	244	heaters on
094316		heimann	3.7 kft	014	shutter open
094328		JW	4.1 kft	034	on
094854		JW	9.0 kft	059	zero
094913		nev	9.0 kft	057	zero
094942		psap	9.0 kft	056	pump on
095004		twc	9.0 kft	057	power recycled
095044		psap	9.0 kft	058	pump off
095609		twc	9.0 kft	058	operating
095644	100431	Profile 1	9.0 - 1.3 kft	038	1300ft
100431	102405	Run 1.1	1.3 kft	097	1300ft
100524		bbr	1.3 kft	118	retract
100635		psap	1.3 kft	117	flow on
100846		heimann	1.3 kft	115	cal 08
101213		WP40	1.3 kft	183	
101525		heimann	1.3 kft	184	cal 08
102405	102430	Profile 2	1.3 - 1.0 kft	184	
102430	111208	Run 2.1	1.0 kft	184	wp44
102814		WP41	1.0 kft	196	
103805		cgps	1.0 kft	194	recording
103823		wrxr	1.0 kft	194	unable to connect
105345		psap	1.0 kft	239	flow off
105548		wp43	1.0 kft	266	
105945		psap	1.0 kft	270	flow on
111440	115811	Run 2.2	1.0 kft	092	
111527		nev	1.0 kft	094	zero
111609		JW	1.0 kft	094	zero
111941		heimann	1.0 kft	094	cal 08
112238		Video	1.0 kft	094	1 (ffc) & 2 (dfc) end
112317		Video	1.0 kft	094	3 (ffc) & 4 (dfc) start
112811		wp43	1.0 kft	052	
114030		WP42	1.0 kft	003	
114244		psap	1.1 kft	009	flow off
115019		!	1.0 kft	009	water seen on rfc window
115812	122815	Profile 3	1.0 - 30.0 kft	359	
120732		psap	9.7 kft	000	flow on
121543		wrxr	17.9 kft	359	booted on third attempt
122815	123124	Run 3.1	30.0 kft	001	
123421	124517	Run 3.2	30.0 kft	216	
123617		video	30.0 kft	219	4 changed to ufc
123914		JW	30.0 kft	219	zero
123931		nev	30.0 kft	218	zero
124818	125029	Orbit 1	30.0 kft	353	010M start
125150	125346	Orbit 2	30.1 - 30.0 kft	061	065M start
125538	125737	Orbit 3	30.2 - 30.0 kft	137	140M start
125905	130108	Orbit 4	30.2 - 29.9 kft	217	330M start
130144		!	30.2 kft	272	end science
130705		wrxr	25.4 kft	221	now recording
131134		Video	20.9 kft	223	3 & 4 ended during orbits
132509		bbr	7.4 kft	227	extend
132523		heimann	7.0 kft	227	shutter closed
133445		Land	0.38 kft	215	Cranfield

B293 Track 12-JUN-07

FAAM Sortie Brief

GERBIL TEST Flight + VISURB-UK: Assessment of aerosol properties related to urban visibility

Flight No: B293

Date: 12th June 2007

Trial objectives:

1. Full instrumentation shakedown in preparation for GERBIL, including aerosol in-situ measurements and radiometers.
2. Carry out in-situ sampling of urban-pollution aerosols around the UK, and their effect on radiation

Location: Echo and Foxtrot.

Around the coast of SE England from the Wash to the Isle of Wight.

Desired weather:

High loadings of atmospheric aerosols. Cloudless skies preferred, but not essential. Try to avoid sea fog and cloud with bases below 1000ft.

Special requirements:

Check the mesoscale model forecast for the position of aerosol plumes and any showers before flying.

Instruments of particular importance:

Nephelometers (run both as dry)

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

SWS

SHIMS

AIRES

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield at 10Z (11L).
2. Transit towards AMPEP point 87, perform a profile descent at 1000ft/minute to 500ft to arrive at AMPEP point 87.
3. Perform a SLR at 500ft (wherever possible) heading clockwise around the coast as far as AMPEP point 44. The routing suggested is AMPEP points: 87->40->41->42->43->44
4. If meteorological conditions permit, perform a series of banked orbits (e.g. 50degrees at 500ft) at a position determined by the mission scientist.
5. At AMPEP point 44 make reciprocal turn.
6. Return back around coast at 500ft following AMPEP points 44>43>42>41.
7. At point 41 profile ascent to FL300 at 1000ft/min. Continue north at FL300 to AMPEP points 40>83>82. Try to intersect cloud at some point if not already done so during flight.
8. Make reciprocal turn at point 82 and return back via 82>83>87 at FL300.
9. Return to Cranfield.

FAAM Sortie debrief - Flight B293, 12th June 2007

GERBIL testflight & VISURB case study – Mission Scientist Ben Johnson

Objectives:

1. Test all aerosol insitu instruments and aerosol-relevant radiometers.
2. Measure concentrations of pollution around the UK as part of VISURB project.

Weather:

High loadings of UK and European aerosol around the UK due to light easterly or stagnant flow over Southern UK during previous few days. Winds had turned light westerly over preceding 12-24hrs starting to clear pollution away from the West but leaving high aerosol amounts over North sea off East Anglia and Eastern half of English channel.

Low cloud / Sea fog was an intermittent problem over the ocean, preventing aircraft from running at 500ft. Most of Southern England was overcast with BL stratocumulus. Showers developed over eastern England land areas in the afternoon but did not interfere with the flight. Boundary layer height (top of aerosol layer) was around 5000-6000ft. Humidity was very high all through the BL and visibility was generally quite low due to hydrated aerosol, particularly over sea areas.

Flight plans:

This flight involved low-level runs around the English coast from the wash through to the Isle of Wight at 1000-1300ft measuring high aerosol concentrations. High level SLRs and 4 orbits at FL300 over North Sea.

Take off from Cranfield at 09:40Z. Transit to Wash. Profile descent into AMPEP point 87 (Wash area). Followed the usual VISURB path via AMPEP points as far as point 44 (just east of the Isle of Wight. Then back round to 15 miles north of point 41. The first 15 minutes was at 1,300ft then the rest at 1000ft. Cloud was encountered briefly a couple of times during the outbound (clockwise) leg. Otherwise the relative humidity was generally around 95-99%. Cloud was accompanied by an interesting rise then sudden declines in nephelometer scattering when going into cloud. Nephelometer internal relative humidity was not producing believable or sensible looking output during much of the low-level part of the flight. It was reading 65% +/- a very small number for a long time. The pollution plume from London was very clear in the NO_x, NO and NO₂, and somewhat evident in the Nephelometer. CO was not operated / running.

A profile ascent at 1000ft/min was made from 1000ft to FL3000, starting just north of point 41 and travelling up to point 85. A 5 min SLR was made at FL300 until furthest point was reached. A reciprocal turn was made and a 10min SLR was flow travelling SSW back towards East Anglia, followed by a series of 4 orbits at 45-55 degrees. No cirrus was observed above the aircraft during the 30 mins spent at FL300. Science ended after last orbit with a return to Cranfield. Land at 14:30. Total flight time approx 3:50.

Instrument status:

SWS, BBRs and AIRES, core chemistry and cloud physics seemed to work fine (no major problems to report). Problems found with humidity sensor in Dry Neph. Also, communication problems with the Nephelometers during pre-flight preparation. The dry neph eventually worked after turning off and on a few times. No pre-flight calibration (zeroing) was performed. SATCOM not working.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...293**

 Date **12/6/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10 40	T/0				Overcast, vis ~ 10km, light westerly 18e cloud base ~ 1,500ft cloud top ~ 3,000 more haze above and some cirrus.
<p style="text-align: center;">Nephelometer</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Aerosol best lowest down</p>					
095644	P1	FLO80	1		
100431	End P1	1,300ft	NE		AMPEP 87
100431	P1.1	1,300ft	SE		87 - 40
Hydrated aerosol, with RH ~ 99%, going slightly into cloud on occasions.					
Nephelometer green is ~ 200 x 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻¹					
10:24 ⁵	P2	1300ft 1000ft	S	E Anglia (AMPEP 41)	BL height on P1 was 5000ft Reduce altitude to 1000ft due to visibility improving
102436	R2.1	1000ft			cloud base was ~ 1,500ft Radiometers (BBRs working well)
103000					Relative humidity decreasing to 96%

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...293**

 Date **12/6/07**

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FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
103500	R2.1	1000ft	S		Aerosol pccsp conc risen to 1600
	continuing...	"	"		Nephelometer up to $200 \times 10^{-6} m^{-1}$
	"	"	"		from $150 \times 10^{-6} m$ over previous
	"	"	"		10 mins. Suspect London plume
	"	"	"		as winds are from west
103800	"	"	"		NO, NO ₂ , NOx all risen
	"	"	"		Very dramatically from 2-15 ppbv.
	"	"	"		from London traffic.
104000	"	"	S	OFF Kent	Out of London plume now.
104200	"	"	SW	AMPEP 42	Scraps of cloud below (marine stratocumulus)
100500 - 104500	"	"			Winds 5-10 m/s westerly at low-levels (1000-1300ft)
104300	"	"			
105300	"	"			Encountering cloud, Neph initially rose to $400 \times 10^{-6} m^{-1}$ then fell to $20 \times 10^{-6} m^{-1}$. Recovered to $150 \times 10^{-6} m^{-1}$ once out of cloud. LWC upto $0.15 g m^{-3}$
110500	"	1000ft	W		Neph and NOx, NO ₂ , NO dropping as we pass Sussex → Hampshire. and approach AMPEP 44. This agrees with aerosol forecast.
11208	End R2.1		W	AMPEP 44	Too much cloud so can't didn't do orbits.
11440	R2.2	1000ft	E		Reciprocal turn and heading back along s. coast.
112100	"	"	"		Neph starting to climb again to $100 \times 10^{-6} m^{-1}$.

 NOx
659

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.293**

 Date **12/6/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1128	R2.2	1000ft	E	AMPEP 43	still bits of cloud below occasionally.
	Continuing				Temp 13-15°C
					RH 95-100%
1145				Thomas Estuary	Encountering London plume again as NOx, NO, NO ₂ rising sharply. Small-moderate increase in Neph to $260 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$
					London plume even stronger than before and wider.
		vs			Warmer and more humid in the London plume
115810	End R2.2	1000ft	N		END OF VISURB Part of sortie
115810	P3		N	5 mins N of AMPEP 41.	Climb to FL300 for at
	"		"		AIRIS & SWS at high level work
120100	"		"		Cumulus is humulus ahead
120200	"	4,500ft	N		going through now
	"		"		Fair amount of cloud about
	"		"		in BL and cu rising above
	"		"		Aerosol layer top at 5000ft
	"		"		Quite humid. than inversion
	"		"		and hydrolapse very slight
	"		"		around 6000ft
120700	"	9000ft	N	off E-Anglia	Small at inversion & hydrolapse
					at 9000ft. Mostly above
					Cumulus now

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 293

Date: 12/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:50:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:56:45	100	0.08	185	1	Noise											Start Profile 1 from FL090	
09:57:51	130	0.08	186	1	Noise											FL080	
09:58:45	280	0.09		3	10											FL070	
09:59:55	345	0.08		3	Noise											FL060	
10:00:45	390	0.08	252	3000	1000											FL050	
10:01:45	2300	0.19	421	4000	1000	3	50								12	FL040	
10:02:51	590	0.10	463	1000	3											FL030	
10:03:48	800	0.10	464	100	10											FL020	
10:04:01																End of Profile 1 & start Run 1.1 at 1300'	
10:06:00	725	0.10		10	5												
10:08:00	640	0.10		100	10												
10:10:00	560	0.10	484	1000	2000												
10:12:00	1800	0.08	664	3000	1000	0.5	50								12		
10:14:00	3000	0.08	775	1000	10												
10:16:00	700	0.10	777	100	1												
10:18:00	700	0.10	778	90	1												
10:20:00	710	0.10		50	1												
10:22:00	750	0.10		100	2												
10:24:00	1000	0.09		10	2											1000'	
10:26:00	945	0.09		10	2												
10:28:00	980	0.09		10	1												
10:30:00	805	0.10	779	10	1												
10:32:00	850	0.10		5	1												
10:34:00	1200	0.09		10	1												
10:36:00	1560	0.09		10	1												
10:38:00	890	0.09		5	1												
10:40:00	880	0.09		5	1												
10:42:00	900	0.09		10	1												
10:44:00	945	0.09	780	10	1												
10:46:00	845	0.09		10	1												
10:48:00	820	0.10		10	1												
10:50:00	860	0.10		30	1												
10:52:00	870	0.09		30	1												
10:54:00	1340	0.08	984	4000	2000	2	25								12		
10:56:00	875	0.09	1030	100	20											Synch on FFSSP	
10:58:00	725	0.09	1032	10	1												
11:00:00	775	0.09		10	1												
11:02:00	700	0.09		200	10												
11:04:00	740	0.09		10	1												
11:06:00	700	0.09		5	1												
11:08:00	740	0.09	1033	5	1												
11:10:00	770	0.09		5	1												
11:12:07																End of Run 1	
11:14:44																Start Run 2 at 1000'	
11:15:00	745	0.09		20	1												
11:17:00	770	0.09		5	2												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 293

Date: 12/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:50:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:19:00	790	0.09	1033	5	1												
11:21:00	750	0.09		5	1												
11:23:00	770	0.09		100	10												
11:25:00	810	0.09		10	2												
11:27:00	760	0.10		10	1												
11:29:00	900	0.09		20	1												
11:31:00	900	0.10	1034	10	5												
11:33:00	950	0.10		15	2												
11:35:00	930	0.10		10	2												
11:37:00	830	0.10		5	1												
11:39:00	820	0.09		10	1												
11:41:00	920	0.09		10	2												
11:43:00	1300	0.09		10	3												
11:45:00	1350	0.09		10	3												
11:47:00	1300	0.09	1035	10	1												
11:49:00	1150	0.10		15	1												
11:51:00	1200	0.10		30	2												
11:53:00	1100	0.10		10	1												
11:55:00	1200	0.09		10	1												
11:57:00	1240	0.09	1036	10	1												
11:58:12																End of Run 1.2 & start Profile 3	
11:59:25	640	0.10		15	2											FL020	
12:00:27	500	0.10	1056	1000	1000											FL030	
12:01:31	420	0.10	1057	10	10											FL040	
12:02:39	250	0.10	1062	10	2											FL050	
12:03:46	200	0.10		5	1											FL060	
12:04:55	180	0.10	1063	5	1											FL070	
12:05:41	80	0.09	1071	2000	2000											FL080	
12:06:52	30	0.09	1203	1	1	10	200									FL090	
12:07:55	50	0.08	1206	10	1											FL100	
12:08:54	30	0.08		1												FL110	
12:09:55	16	0.08		1	1											FL120	
12:10:43	15	0.07		1	1											FL130	
12:11:46	10	0.07		1	1											FL140	
12:12:41	8	0.08		1	1											FL150	
12:13:47	7	0.09		1	Noise											FL160	
12:14:51	5	0.08		1	Noise											FL170	
12:15:51	7	0.08		1	Noise											FL180	
12:16:52	2	0.06		1	Noise											FL190	
12:17:45	1	0.05		1	Noise											FL200	
12:18:44	1	0.03		1	Noise											FL210	
12:21:56	0			1	Noise											FL240	
12:22:56	0				Noise											FL250	
12:24:00	0			1	Noise											FL260	
12:25:02	0				Noise											FL270	
12:26:28	0			1	Noise											FL280	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B293

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Date: 12/JUNE/07 Operator(s): S. ROGER

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: Pre GERBICS Test Flight. — S.E coast from the Wash to 10W

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
07 28 33	On the ground	1 x 60	CBS	C	71	31	
07 29 20		"	H	C	71	31	
07 09 40	TAKE OFF						
09 56.	P1 ↓						
09 04 31	R1/1300ft	1 x 60	C	<			
09 05 20		"	H	C	71	32	
09 06 21		240 x 1	N	C	71	32	In clouds Sea calm
09 09		120' x 1	Z	○	70	31	Highly variable signal - lumpy cloud?
09 10 55		1 x 60	C	<	71	31	
09 11 41		"	H	C	71	31	Turn in cloud waypoint 40
09 12 40		240 x 1	N	C	71	30	
09 15 03		1 x 60	CBS	C	71	31	
09 15 40		"	HBB	C	71	31	
09 16 40		240 x 1	N	C	71	31	Possible ship plume?
09 19 07		1 x 60	C	<	71	31	
09 19 50		"	H	C	71	31	
09 20 42		120 x 1	Z	○	70	31	Gaps in the cloud above.
09 22 31		1 x 60	C	<	71	31	
09 23 10		"	H	C			↙ descending P2 ↓
09 24 38	R1-2 1000ft	360 x 1	N	C	71	31	
09 27 50		1 x 60	C	<	71	31	
09 28 28		"	H	C	71	30	
09 29 20		120 x 1	Z	○	70	31	Thin cloud above.
09 31 30		1 x 60	C	<	71	31	
09 32 10		"	H	C	71	31	
09 33 00		360 x 1	N	C	71	31	
09 36 11		1 x 60	C	<	71	31	?
09 37 07		1 x 60	C	<	71	31	
09 37 44		"	H	C	71	30	
09 38 51		120 x 1 240 x 1	Z	○	70	30	A little bumps
09 40 55		1 x 60	C	<	71	31	

ARIES flight log

Flight:

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Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A:

B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
09 41 40	1000 ft.	1x60	H.	C	71	31	
09 42 35		360 x 1	N	C	71	31	← 777 N? In very thin haze. Cloud below.
09 46 20		1x60	C	C	71	31	
09 48 58		"	H	C	71	31	
09 47 43		360 x 1	N	C	71	31	Thin wisps of cloud below. See fairly calm
09 51.00		1x60	C	C	71	31	
09 51 39		"	H	C	71	31	
09 52 25		360 x 1	N	C	71	31	Into cloud 09 53 25-ish → 09 54 40 out
09 55 48		1x60	C	C	71	31	
09 56 35		"	H	C	71	31	
09 57 23		120 x 1	Z	○	70	31	Thin haze above.
09 59 30		1x60	C	C	71	31	
10 00 13		"	H	C	71	31	
10 01 00		360 x 1	N	C	71	31	
10 04 13		1x60	C	C	71	31	
10 04 51		"	H	C	71	31	
10 05 45		360 x 1	N	C	71	31	10 08 20 crossing ship track.
10 09 00		1x60	C	C	71	31	
10 09 38		"	H	C	71	31	
10 10 36		120 x 1	Z	○	70	31	Thin + patchy above.
10 12 42		1x60	H	C	71	31	E of R 10 12.
10 13 24		"	C	C	71	31	
10 14 03		"	H	C	71	31	
	RZ.2						
10 15 30		1x60	C	C	71	31	
10 16 07		"	H	C	71	31	
10 16 50		360 x 1	N	C	71	31	
10 20 05		1x60	C	C	71	31	
10 20 45		"	H	C	71	31	
10 21 46		120 x 1	Z	○	70	31	Cloud above.
10 24 00		1x60	C	C	71	31	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B293

page 3 of 4

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
10 24 37	loop h.	1x60	H	C	71	31	
10 25 40		360x1	N	C	71	31	10 27 52 turn. Point 43.
10 28 52		1x60	C	C	71	31.	
10 29 30		"	H	C	71	32.	
10 30 26		360x1	N	C	71	31	Cloud below - some gap
10 33 37		1x60	C	C	71	31	
10 34 14		"	H	C	71	31.	
10 35 05		120x1	Z	O	70	30.	Hazy above
10 37 09		1x60	C	C	71	31	
10 37 45		"	H	C	71	31	
10 38 30		360x1	N	C	71	31	Slight haze below. 10 40 14 Turn Point 42
10 42 11		1x60	C	C	71	31	A bit bumpy
10 42 55		"	"	"			
10 43 32		"	H	C	71	31.	
10 44 22		360x1	Z	O	70	30	Oops 360x1 (intended 120x1)
10 48 32		1x60	C	C	71	32.	
10 49 12		"	H	C	71	32	
10 49 53		360x1	N	C	71	31.	
10 53 03		1x60	C	C	71	31.	
10 53 37		"	H	C	71	31	
10 54 43		240 x1	N	C	71	31	Hazy.
10 56 56		1x60	C	C	71	31	
10 57 34		"	H	C	71	31.	
11 58 12	P3A						
11 28 15	R3.1						
11 28 35	FL300	1x60	C	C	71	31	Cloud below 8/8 Clear above.
11 29 20		"	H	C	71	31	
11 30 10		360x1	N	C	71	31	Ear 11:31:24
11 33 23		1x60	C	C	71	31	
11 33 58	R3.2	"	H	C	71	31	
11 35 33			C				

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	12/06/07	Flight	B293	log pages	2
Operator(s)	King Pollard		Campaign	GERBIL Test			
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield			

System start

MARSS **Not Operated**

Visual pod inspection						
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						
FERA on	at time					
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16		Ch		Ch18	
Temperature controller set points			17		-20	
MARSS CPU on	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							X
Turn on Deimos CPU							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Start Deimos Software	at time						07:35:05
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating							X
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual			X
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			09:24:36
Brightness temps 'sensible'						
Target temps	MARSS:		Hot		Cold	
	Deimos:		Hot 344.83		Cold 304.93	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	46.82	47.03	55	54.34		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					

B293_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

09:31:23.14 --- - - - -
09:31:23.14 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:31:23.14 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                                tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:31:23.14 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B293
09:31:23.14 --- - - - -
09:31:29.57 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
09:31:35.91 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
09:33:05.05 --- - - - -
09:33:05.05 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:33:05.05 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                                tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:33:05.05 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B293
09:33:05.05 --- - - - -
09:33:42.22 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:34:02.86 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:34:06.03 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:34:45.34 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:34:49.34 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:35:05.32 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:35:05.32 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:35:05.35 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:35:06.79 USH - - - - Idling
09:35:06.86 LSH - - - - Idling
09:35:06.92 SWS - - - - Idling
09:35:24.04 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:35:24.04 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:35:24.05 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:35:48.13 SWS - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:35:53.29 SWS - - - 750 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:36:33.03 USH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
09:36:38.36 USH - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
09:36:44.39 USH - - - 750 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:36:51.76 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:37:00.68 LSH - - - 750 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:38:54.42 --- - - - - *** test
09:39:23.97 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
09:39:27.67 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
09:39:44.75 --- - - - - *** 140 rear for take off
09:40:59.79 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:41:07.73 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:43:24.71 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 200ms.
09:43:28.90 SWS - - 100 - NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 100ms.
09:43:54.58 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
09:43:58.13 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:44:01.95 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
09:44:06.95 SWS - - 15 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
09:44:15.35 USH - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 150ms.
09:44:29.84 USH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 50ms.
09:44:34.32 USH - - - 500 - NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
09:44:37.93 LSH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 50ms.
09:44:44.90 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:44:45.08 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:44:45.08 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:44:46.55 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:44:50.76 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:44:52.86 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:06:16.26 SWS - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 250ms.
10:06:19.83 SWS - - 500 - NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 500ms.
10:06:25.24 LSH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 500ms.
10:06:33.64 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:06:33.67 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:06:33.88 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:06:39.08 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:06:39.30 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:06:41.98 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:06:46.43 --- - - - - Reset shutters.

```

10:06:52.04	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:07:05.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:10.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:10.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:14.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:16.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:22.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:05.67	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
10:36:09.46	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
10:36:13.66	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
10:36:43.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:43.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:43.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:49.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:51.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:52.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:25.48	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
10:42:30.73	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
10:42:35.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:42:35.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:42:35.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:42:40.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:43.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:43.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:03.61	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:49:09.44	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
10:49:13.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:14.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:14.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:19.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:21.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:22.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:15.82	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
10:53:20.32	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
10:53:23.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:23.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:23.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:26.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:28.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:31.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:56.87	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
11:00:58.82	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:02:52.95	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 400ms.
11:02:56.16	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
11:03:01.17	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
11:11:15.50	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:11:19.25	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 75ms.
11:11:31.86	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
11:11:35.73	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
11:11:42.58	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
11:11:51.32	USH	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
11:11:56.46	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
11:12:00.74	USH	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
11:12:03.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:12:04.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:12:04.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:12:06.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:12:07.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:12:12.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:06.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** start r2.2
11:17:09.36	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
11:17:13.91	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 500ms.
11:17:39.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:39.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:39.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:44.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:44.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:47.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:55:13.63	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.

11:55:21.58	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 250ms.
11:55:27.05	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
11:55:32.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:32.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:32.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:34.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:55:37.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:55:40.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:00.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of climb....sws to 8 deg fore
12:13:33.63	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:13:42.19	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 250ms.
12:13:46.56	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
12:13:49.82	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
12:13:53.22	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
12:14:04.20	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
12:14:09.80	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
12:14:13.38	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
12:14:16.21	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
12:14:24.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:14:24.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:14:24.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:14:29.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:32.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:32.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:37.90	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
12:16:42.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:50.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:10.12	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
12:25:18.21	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 300ms.
12:25:24.25	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 350ms.
12:25:29.60	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
12:25:33.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:25:33.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:25:34.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:25:39.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:41.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:42.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:22.58	LSH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
12:27:24.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:32.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:31:20.37	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
12:31:25.20	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
12:31:27.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:31:32.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:34:36.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** start r3.2
12:44:46.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** start orbit 1 60deg AOB
12:44:47.05	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:45:12.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** CORRECTION..NOT IN ORBIT YET
12:45:27.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** end r3.2
12:48:46.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** start orbit 1 60deg AOB
12:48:57.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** 45deg AOB
12:50:33.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** end orbit 1
12:51:50.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** start orbit 2
12:52:12.62	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 15ms.
12:52:17.14	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
12:52:37.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50deg AOB
12:52:50.14	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 50ms.
12:53:00.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:00.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:00.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:04.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:05.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:06.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:21.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** setting up for next orbit
12:53:52.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** end orbit 2
12:55:39.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** start orbit 3
12:55:58.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50deg AOB
12:57:55.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:55.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:57:55.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:00.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:01.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:01.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:03.97	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
12:58:06.60	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
12:58:09.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:14.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:37.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** end orbit 3
12:59:05.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** start orbit 4
12:59:24.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** 47deg AOB
13:00:44.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** good orbit datwise
13:01:08.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** end orbit 4
13:01:59.27	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
13:02:01.81	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
13:02:03.88	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
13:02:08.13	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
13:02:12.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:12.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:12.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:17.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:02:17.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:02:20.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:05:00.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** end science

Flight:

B293

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nezvorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:40:52

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

14/06/2007 17:28:28

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B293

Date: 12 June 2007

Instruments

1. Satcom phone not working, installation not complete
2. Satcom messages being sent 'successful' but not received.
3. Satcom position reports are queued, but never sent
4. Downward facing camera cycling contrast control
5. WXRX unable to connect via VNC, rebooted on third try.
6. dry neph relative humidity suspect – being investigated
7. dry neph initialisation scheme – painful comms problem
8. nevz total water unit does not 'balance' when zero'd

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

Not working

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 12/6/07

Flight No: 6293

Pre-Flighter: sed

Item	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	INOP
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	NOT FITTED
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	NOT FITTED
27	<input type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf ▶

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	<i>WINDINGS POOR</i>
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	<i>NOT NEEDED.</i>
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed <i>[Signature]</i>
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		<i>NOT NEEDED</i>
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Traps empty (weekly only)		<i>[Signature]</i>

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B293:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Nephelometer	No operator on GERBIL

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	05 Sep 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
1 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras
2 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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